

NATURANCE

Nature for insurance,
insurance for nature

(Grant Agreement 101060464)

**Deliverable D3.2 - *Equitable and
sustainable business models***

WP3 – Governance

Version 1.0 | September 2025

HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-06 - Nature-based solutions, prevention
and reduction of risks and the insurance sector

Deliverable Title	Equitable and sustainable business models
Brief Description	Designing insurance solutions that incorporate climate risk reduction, nature and equity – what lessons can be learnt?
WP number	WP3
Lead Beneficiary	LSE Grantham Research Institute
Author(s)	Pranav Shankar Kaundinya, Zuzanna Kozłowska, Laura Clavey, Swenja Surminski, Stefano Ceolotto, Giada Bastanzi, JoAnne Linnerooth-Bayer, Tim Foreman Internal reviewers: Neil Gunn
Deliverable Due Date	30/09/2025
Actual Delivery Date	30/09/2025
Nature of the Deliverable	R – Report
Dissemination Level	PU - Public

Document History

Date	Ver.	Contributors	Comment
12/09/2025	0.1	Zuzanna Kozłowska	Draft for review
19/09/2025	0.2	Swenja Surminski, Pranav Shankar Kaundinya, Laura Clavey, Zuzanna Kozłowska	Review
24/09/2025	0.3	Swenja Surminski	Review
27/09/2025	0.4	Pranav Shankar Kaundinya, Zuzanna Kozłowska	Final revisions
29/09/2025	1.0	Laura Clavey, Zuzanna Kozłowska, Pranav Shankar Kaundinya	Final review

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	6
2. The need for innovative solutions that address multiple societal challenges	8
3. Context of different design considerations and success criteria for insurance schemes	10
4. Exploring concepts to help guide inclusion of risk reduction, social equity and nature within insurance schemes	12
4.1 Risk reduction	12
4.2 The social equity dimension	12
4.3 Nature	16
5. Insights from design and implementation of different insurance schemes	19
5.1 Flood Re	19
5.2 CMCC - Community Insurance for Controlled Flooding	21
5.3 ORRAA - Parametric Insurance for Coral Reef Recovery: The MAR Fund Model	24
5.4 InsuResilience - The Coffee Climate Protection Insurance (CCPI) Model	25
5.5 Wesselényi Miklós Fund - Co-designing an Equitable National Flood Insurance System	27
6. Discussion: emerging guidance for those tasked with exploring, designing and implementing insurance schemes	31
7. Challenges and opportunities for practically advancing equitable and sustainable insurance models	35
References	37

Executive Summary

Climate change and nature loss are converging crises that intensify disaster risks and undermine ecosystem resilience. Nature-based solutions (NbS), including wetlands, urban tree cover, and coral reefs, are powerful tools that can address multiple societal challenges at once, such as ecosystem restoration and climate adaptation and mitigation. However, their implementation must be carefully designed to ensure both environmental sustainability and social equity.

Insurance is increasingly recognised as a mechanism to support climate adaptation by redistributing risk, accelerating recovery, and incentivising resilience. When integrated with NbS, insurance schemes can deliver co-benefits for nature and communities. Yet, these schemes must be context-specific, financially viable, and socially just to avoid unintended consequences.

This report explores how insurance models can be designed to incorporate equity and environmental sustainability. It explores how the concepts of risk reduction, social equity and nature can be embedded into the design of insurance schemes, unpacking and providing insights from existing frameworks. An assessment of case studies demonstrate diverse architectures of schemes and identifies five key insights:

- **There are multiple possible configurations of insurance schemes:** There are multiple ways to configure private, public and third sector actors. It is crucial to consider which configuration offers the best fit for purpose for any insurance scheme given local context and needs.
- **There remains variation in levels of stakeholder engagement:** How a scheme engages the stakeholders involved influences how it evolves and whom it serves.
- **There is a need for consistent consideration of nature:** Nature is often viewed secondary to climate, highlighting a need for nature to be consistently embedded into scheme design, including identifying and assessing co-benefits and trade-offs.
- **Risk reduction is incorporated in schemes in different ways and to different extents:** While risk-reduction is gaining prominence as a priority in insurance design, it needs to be fully integrated and its efficacy should be evidenced in order to ensure the long term sustainability and insurability of projects.
- **Balancing the different principles of equity can be complex:** Satisfying multiple aspects of equity can be a balancing act during design and implementation, and requires reflection on the scheme's objective and scope.

The case studies demonstrate that whilst insurance can be utilised as a financial mechanism to address the climate change and nature crises, as well as wider societal issues, its success depends on its structure and implementation. Ultimately, there is no universal blueprint for embedding equity and nature into insurance schemes. Success requires revisiting foundational assumptions, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and designing solutions that are principled, pragmatic, and

adaptable. As climate and nature risks escalate, the need to develop robust, inclusive, and sustainable insurance models becomes ever more urgent.

1. Introduction

As climate change progresses and accelerates so has the magnitude and frequency of a variety of physical climate risks, in particular, heatwaves, floods and storms. 2025 has been a challenging year for climate adaptation, being the warmest on record, while the continued underinvestment in climate adaptation necessitates increased private sector involvement in funding interventions. With the rising probability of extreme events, heightened exposure of populations to catastrophes and greater vulnerability, particularly post-COVID, climate adaptation is essential to ensure the achievement of international development objectives (UNEP, 2024a; IFRC, 2025).

Compounding this issue is the nature and biodiversity crisis. With ecosystems providing vital ecosystem services such as global climate regulation, flood mitigation and storm mitigation, the loss and degradation of ecosystems increases the challenge of climate change adaptation as well as providing challenges in its own right. As of 2019, 75% of land surface was found to be significantly altered, over 85% of wetland area had been lost and the average abundance of native species in most major terrestrial biomes had fallen by at least 20% (IPBES, 2019).

In the context of tightening public sector purse-strings, insurance is increasingly seen as a solution to divert more capital into climate adaptation, redistributing the burdens and costs of recovering, accelerating rebuilding post-disaster and even promoting risk reduction to improve resilience (Jarzabkowski et al., 2019). Moreover, innovative insurance solutions that utilise nature-based solutions (NbS) can produce co-benefits for nature, helping to address the joint crises of climate and nature concurrently. Insurance's role as a tool to tackle societal issues is set to rise in the next decades, necessitating careful policy and insurance design to achieve key objectives.

This report showcases how existing insurance schemes have considered equity and environmental sustainability within their design and offers insights to those considering the design or implementation of new insurance schemes. Whilst the scope of this report showcases insurance schemes that primarily address climate adaptation, we consider how co-benefits for nature, such as through NbS, have been incorporated. This report may also be of benefit to those designing insurance schemes to address societal challenges other than climate change.

We begin by introducing the need for insurance schemes to address societal challenges, followed by exploring the terms 'equitable' and 'sustainable' and then analysing four case studies through the lens of the following questions:

1. What is the scheme's solution design and how does it address risk reduction?
2. How has nature been considered and incorporated?
3. How has the scheme performed in general?
4. How have questions of equity and fairness been addressed?

The analysis unpacks the different perspectives and approaches and highlights key lessons learned for those designing insurance schemes. We conclude that insurance is a financial mechanism which, depending on structure and implementation, can be utilised to address the climate change

and nature crises, as well as wider societal issues. There is a need for continued conversation between practitioners, communities, policy-makers and donors to strike a balance between a principled and pragmatic solution design, as well as a need to revisit the fundamental assumptions and logics a climate risk and natural asset insurance policy is built and operated on.

Terminology is important, and particularly in the field of sustainability, insurance, climate and nature there can easily be misunderstandings about meaning and interpretation of concepts across different stakeholder groups. Therefore within this report, we use key terms as per the following definitions.

Key terms

- **Sustainable Business Model:** A sustainable business model is a business model that meets the definition of sustainability, in that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland, 1987). To be sustainable, a business model should consider the three pillars of sustainability: social, economic and environmental. Within this report, we consider the sustainability of business models related to insurance schemes.
- **Financial Sustainability:** Ability of an organisation to maintain financial stability over the long term while meeting its operational and strategic goals (Irianto & Adiatma, 2023)
- **Insurance:** Form of risk transfer, where coverage of a risk is obtained from an insurer in exchange for ongoing premiums paid to the insurer (UNDRR, 2017)
- **Nature-based Solutions:** actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified ecosystems that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously benefiting people and nature (IUCN, 2020). Within this report, NbS are discussed in the context of adapting to climate change, however they can also be applied more widely to address other societal challenges, such as human health or food security.
- **Risk reduction:** Refers to identifying and managing hazard to reduce potential loss in relation to climate change (Surminski, 2013).
- **Risk transfer:** Refers to mechanisms that involve transferring the future potential risk (and arising liabilities) from one party to another in exchange for an agreed premium (Surminski, 2013).

2. The need for innovative solutions that address multiple societal challenges

The Earth's average temperature registered 1.52°C above the pre-Industrial Era average in 2025, exceeding this key climate threshold for the first time (Forster et al., 2025). According to the 6th Assessment Report of the IPCC (2022), climbing atmospheric and ocean temperatures have led to an increased frequency of extreme temperatures (i.e., heatwaves), volatility in precipitation and natural catastrophes such as wildfires, floods, landslides and storms. This has substantially impacted society and nature, leading to widespread ecosystem degradation, infrastructure breakdowns, financial losses and mortality (IPCC, 2022). As of 2024, it is estimated that climate-driven natural catastrophes (excluding non-atmospheric events like earthquakes or volcanic activity) directly led to losses of US\$ 402 billion globally, of which around US\$ 151 billion had been covered by the insurance industry (Gallagher Re, 2025). Closer to home, the European Continent has been warming at twice the global rate, leading to an even faster increase in climate-driven disasters in a region challenged with an aging population, economic slowdown and rising global tensions. Projections show that the intensity and frequency of natural catastrophes across Europe will continue to rise even in the most optimistic Paris target-aligned scenarios (European Environment Agency [EEA], 2024). Overall, the rapid rise in climate risk has been driven by a combination of increased hazards driven by altering climate and greater exposure of people, nature and assets to these hazards that limit post-disaster recovery and rebuilding (UNDRR, 2024).

The Earth is also facing a concurrent nature crisis. The 2019 IPBES Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services found that 25% of plants and animals are threatened with extinction as a result of human activity, biodiversity in natural ecosystems had declined 47% compared to earliest estimates states and 75% of land surface is significantly altered (IPBES, 2019). Nature provides vital ecosystem services that humans rely on, including provision of food, medicine, materials and genetic resources, sustaining freshwater, soil and air quality, regulating the climate and providing pest control (IPBES, 2019). The degradation of ecosystems and loss of diversity therefore poses societal challenges, including serious risk to global food security by undermining the resilience of many agricultural systems, as well as leading to cascading effects resulting in water shortages (IPBES, 2019). Direct drivers of nature change include changes in land and sea use, exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution and invasion of alien species. These drivers are underpinned by societal values and human behaviours (IPBES, 2019). Future cashflows depend on the resilience of ecosystems, with estimations losses of at least 10 trillion of GDP will be lost by 2050 due to the decline in ecosystem services if nature is not protected (CISL, 2022; WEF 2020) and \$44 trillion of economic value generation being estimated to be moderately or highly dependent on nature (WEF, 2020).

The climate and nature crises cannot be considered independently. Climate change is a direct driver of nature change that exacerbates the impact of other drivers (IPBES, 2019), and ecosystems play a vital role in climate change mitigation and adaptation (Munang et al., 2013). For example, terrestrial biodiversity distribution is primarily shaped by climatic conditions (WWF,

2020) and natural carbon sinks such as forests and the ocean absorb half of human produced carbon emissions (Howarth and Robinson, 2024; WWF, 2020). Ecosystems also provide natural climate adaptation solutions, with natural wetlands storing water for times of drought, urban tree cover providing cooling power and mangroves and coral reefs providing protection from coastal flooding (UNEP, 2020; WWF 2020). There are therefore cascading effects between climate change impacts, ecosystem loss and degradation and the increased risk of climate-related disasters (Munang et al., 2013; TNFD, 2023).

The joint challenges create a need for approaches that address both crises at once, such as NbS for climate change, which are actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified ecosystems whilst also addressing climate adaptation and/or mitigation (IUCN, 2020). Further discussed in section 3, financial services and the insurance industry play a key role in catalysing innovative solutions to societal challenges including climate adaptation and nature loss. It is essential to ensure that solutions take into account the co-benefits and trade-offs between climate change and nature, as well as other societal issues (TNFD, 2023).

3. Context of different design considerations and success criteria for insurance schemes

The standard aspects to consider when exploring the viability of insurance or designing schemes are affordability, commercial viability, and financial sustainability. These aspects can be in conflict for example when trying to make coverage accessible to those at risk (affordability) while ensuring that the insurance provider remains profitable now and in the future (commercial viability and financial sustainability). In order to measure and monitor these criteria a number of metrics are being used, as summarized in Table 1, building on Surminski and Hudson (2017).

Table 1: Variables and associated metrics of insurance

Term	Definition	Metrics used
Affordability	Cost effectiveness of an insurance product from the perspective of the consumer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average Premium Paid / Average Coverage Amount (Michel-Kerjan and Kousky, 2010; Michel-Kerjan, 2010) • Premium paid/expected insured losses; Premium spent/income (Blumbey et al., 2007; Stone, 2010) • Price elasticity of insurance (Tooth, 2007)
Commercial Viability/ Availability	Demand of an insurance product to the particular market segment the product is designed for and the potential risk-adjusted profit and the matching supply of insurance cover.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Administrative Cost + Indemnity Payments)/Premium Payments (Hazell, 1992) • Opportunity cost of money held in reserves (Bardsley et al., 1984) • Number of Insureds/Number of Eligible Persons (Swiss Re, 2013) • Potential revenues = (number of insured + number of potentially insured) x average premium, including returns from investing accumulated premium in equity markets • Public financial backing
Financial Sustainability/ Solvency	<p>Short Term - Operating income is sufficient to cover operating costs, including salaries and wages, supplies, loan losses, and other administrative costs.</p> <p>Long Term - Operating income and capital is sufficient to cover costs of funds and other forms of subsidies received when they are valued at market rates (Definition from Meyer, 2002)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Administrative Cost + Indemnity Payments)/ Premium Payments (Hazell, 1992) • Administrative Cost + Indemnity Payments/ Non-Subsidized Premium Payments (Mahul and Stutley, 2010) • Solvency Ratios

Source: Surminski and Hudson, 2017

Extending the scope of insurance to wider societal and environmental considerations

Given the challenges arising from rising risk levels, over the last two decades there has been a growing focus on utilizing insurance so that it not only delivers its core risk transfer function but also addresses risk drivers by influencing levels of risk, for example, through incentivisation of risk reduction initiatives.

This extension of insurance considerations is particularly visible in the context of projects aimed at most vulnerable populations for example in developing countries, often funded by donors or developed in collaboration with NGOs. Here the concepts of equity and social benefit are important, as illustrated by for example the pro-poor principles developed by Munich Climate Insurance Initiative (MCII) (see section 4).

A further extension of the role of insurance comes in the context of nature and NbS, particularly in the context of reducing physical risks by harnessing nature's ability to protect assets and cities from events such as floods (Tyllianakis et al., 2022): For example mangroves reduce annual flood damages by over \$82 billion (Beck et al., 2018), with pioneering insurance mechanisms now designed to protect these ecosystems, such as the Caribbean's parametric cover which helps restore mangroves forests after damage (The Nature Conservancy, 2020). Similarly, wetlands demonstrate an important risk reduction benefit, having decreased flood losses by \$625 million during Hurricane Sandy in 2012 (Narayan, et al., 2017), with ongoing efforts underway aimed at recognising their risk-reduction benefits in insurance pricing (Ooms, 2025).

Therefore in addition to achieving its core risk transfer solutions in an affordable, commercially viable and financially sustainable way an insurance scheme would also positively contribute to climate risk reduction and nature restoration (Marchal et al., 2019) for example through the development of novel risk finance mechanisms for nature (Marchal et al., 2023) or by incentivising NbS. A key question is how those tasked with designing or implementing insurance schemes navigate the complexity of the increasing number of success criteria for insurance schemes.

4. Exploring concepts to help guide inclusion of risk reduction, social equity and nature within insurance schemes

This section unpacks key concepts and provides insights from existing frameworks to help guide the inclusion of risk reduction, social equity and nature into insurance scheme design. Importantly, there is no universally applicable template of design criteria and metrics as insurance scheme design is context specific and subject to often very lengthy engagements, deliberations and negotiations between different stakeholders to accommodate varying priorities and achieve practical compromise. However, there are a range of frameworks, principles and concepts that can help develop sustainable insurance solutions.

4.1 Risk reduction

An example of a risk reduction approach was developed by Surminski and Oramas-Dorta (2011), who looked at different degrees of linkages between risk transfer and risk reduction across schemes in emerging and developing countries. They differentiated between:

1. Indirect Association: where risk transfer is considered one element within an overall policy framework or strategy for disaster risk reduction or adaptation
2. Direct Association: where a risk transfer scheme explicitly supports risk reduction efforts as part of its operation.

According to this approach the risk reduction element of insurance can manifest itself in different ways:

- It can be **compulsory** - when proof of risk reduction becomes mandatory in order to be eligible for insurance;
- It can be **positively incentivised** - for example, when risk reduction measures taken by policyholders are rewarded through better policy terms or premium discounts;
- It can be **encouraged** through risk awareness building - for example, when insurance schemes share risk and resilience information with the insured; and
- It can **deliver risk reduction** through building back better provisions or no-claims discounts being invested in resilience measures.

According to a 2012 database (ClimateWise, 2012), just over one-third of schemes offered explicit support for risk reduction. In a follow-up investigation of insurance schemes in Asia, Surminski, Panda, & Lambert (2019) find that this number has gone up, with several promising examples, but it is far from being mainstreamed, as illustrated in Bouchard et al. (2022). These findings illustrate a gradual but important shift: insurance is no longer being assessed solely on its ability to compensate for losses after disasters, but also on its contribution to building resilience before disasters occur.

4.2 The social equity dimension

The words equity, social justice and fairness have been used interchangeably, often being left undefined or ill-defined across theories, discourse and frameworks. Recent reviews of the use of

the terms evidence the lack of consistent definition, rendering the space nebulous and less navigable (Walker et al., 2024; Coggins et al., 2021). A few commonly identified frameworks of equity in the context of climate impacts, adaptation and insurance have emerged in the literature (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Equity Frameworks (own visualisation)

The **'Schlosberg Trio'** (Schlosberg, 2003) approach consists of three distinct forms of equity: distributive, procedural and recognitional, and has been amongst the most widely utilised frameworks in assessing equity in the climate space first put forward in 2003 (Walker et al., 2024; Svarstad & Benjaminsen, 2019). Distributive equity refers to the spread of the burdens and benefits of an intervention across society, space and time. Recognitional equity places weight on whose interests, concerns and views are accounted for when designing an intervention. Procedural equity considers how decisions are made (de Herve, 2021; Grasso, 2010; Juhola et al., 2022). Distributive equity has been given disproportionate attention, resulting in multiple principles of distribution emerging (see Figure 1).

More recent literature has pivoted towards a layered approach, often pointing towards more underlying causes of vulnerability and how these interact with each other. These are often referred to as **'restorative equity'** or **'systemic equity'** which have resulted in complex ideas and framings such as 'flood disadvantage' or 'flood poverty' in the realm of flood-risk management (O'Hare & White, 2017; Cobbing et al., 2024). Given their complexity and the fact that addressing

these systemic challenges require collaboration across multiple divisions of government, this lens may not be practical to apply in a practitioner's context.

The **Stockholm Environmental Institute** proposes a framework that turns attention towards equitable outputs, equitable outcomes and structural change. Equity in outputs means ensuring a fair distribution of the costs, benefits and resource allocation across society for an intervention. Equity in outcomes entails a fair use of resources and prioritising developing capabilities amongst stakeholders to better manage catastrophe risks. Finally, structural change refers to a wider reconfiguration of institutions to address the multiple causes of vulnerability, sustaining the long-run increase in resilience to catastrophes (Shawoo et al., 2024).

In the context of insurance, **Linnerooth-Bayer et al. (2018)** put forward three principles of equity for catastrophe insurance, namely, mutuality, solidarity and accountability (see Figure 2):

- **Mutuality:** The idea that losses are not shared outside of the community at risk. This means that compensation results only from what is paid into the insurance scheme, making it actuarially fair.
- **Solidarity:** The ability-to-pay is accounted for in the price of premiums forming some type of cross-subsidisation to keep insurance within reach of the poorest.
- **Accountability:** Renders stakeholders responsible for the outcomes of a catastrophe by introducing a causal link such as a legal obligation.

Figure 2: Linnerooth-Bayer et al. (2018)'s Principles of Equity (own visualisation)

This approach was conceived in the context of the Loss and Damage narrative, particularly around providing guidance on which countries (or stakeholders) would have to pay for the damages and losses experienced due to climate change.

A framework specifically aimed at helping to design and implement insurance schemes for vulnerable groups in society is offered by the MCII through its '**Pro-Poor Principles**' (Schäfer et al., 2016). These include seven 'guiding principles' that are recommended for designing equitable insurance schemes (see Figure 3):

Figure 3: MCII Pro-poor Principles (Schäfer et al., 2016)

This framework offers a more practitioner-level perspective on promoting equity when implementing insurance.

Affordability and pricing are a central concern for insurance schemes, particularly in the global South. The question around who pays for insurance and how much is at the heart of the effort to utilise insurance to bridge the protection gap. Premium subsidies have long been the favoured strategy to keep insurance affordable for those who need it the most (UNU-EHS, 2025; Betram & Scott, 2024). These subsidies have been preferred as they ensure insurance remains within reach for less vulnerable sections of a population, growing the risk pool and ensuring its viability. While the strategy has proven successful, it comes with a host of challenges including ensuring financial solvency and long-term operational self-sufficiency (Scott et al., 2022). Allocating premium subsidies can be complex, making use of means-tested approaches and exclusions to target those who need it most, and therefore requiring a careful assessment of equity to accurately target the relevant stakeholders.

The ‘**Choice Sensitivity**’ approach (O’Neill & O’Neill, 2012) reflects on the debate of the meaning of ‘risk reflective’ in the context of pricing insurance of which there are three configurations:

- **Pure Actuarial Fairness:** Risk-reflective pricing where individuals pay premiums that are proportional to the magnitude of risk they face. To exemplify, FEMA’s Risk Rating 2.0 prices premiums according to exposure to flooding (Government Accountability Office, 2020).
- **Choice-sensitive Fairness:** The cost of premiums must reflect the risk faced by individuals on the basis of the choices they have made rather than circumstances beyond their control. This relates to the idea of ‘luck egalitarianism’ that argues that risk premiums must reflect ‘choice luck’. However, there have been contentions on how this can be implemented given that those who are poor may not get to choose from the same set of options as those who are well off and the attribution issues around climate change further complicate this (Charpentier et al., 2021). Contrary to Risk Rating 2.0, the National Flood Mitigation Fund from the US National Flood Insurance Programme (NFIP) offers premium discounts if households raise their elevation rendering net premium sensitive to choice (FEMA, 1968).
- **Fairness as Social Justice:** All individuals are guaranteed a minimum access to insurance, (which is understood as a public good and service) regardless of their level of risk. The French CatNat system closely resembles this, providing a universal minimum standard of protection and compensation (Charpentier et al., 2021).

This review of frameworks reveals that introducing equity into insurance entails balancing multiple competing frameworks, reflecting the complexity of balancing actuarial fairness with broader social equity considerations. From a practitioner’s standpoint, these frameworks must be viewed as tools within a toolkit that allow one to articulate the principles they subscribe to and identify rules-of-thumb that are fit for the purpose of the insurance policy and its objectives. In the following sections we investigate how equity can be included in insurance design considerations by reflecting on insights from case studies.

4.3 Nature

Insurance is increasingly being positioned not just as a financial safety net, but also a tool that is linked to nature. Insurance can be linked to nature in a number of different ways:

1. **Bridging the finance gap:** Insurance can help encourage investments in nature that otherwise would be inaccessible, such as insurance-backed conservation, by de-risking the investment in the event of possible losses;
2. **Preserving natural capital:** Insurance for existing natural capital (such as coral reefs or wetlands) can improve capacity to withstand climate damages whilst ensuring preservation of nature. The inclusion of ecosystem condition within premiums creates incentives to maintain the ecosystems and can provide funds for repairing ecosystems if a natural hazard occurs; and

3. **Incentivising NbS:** Insurance could incentivise NbS as a risk-reducing action in addition to or instead of traditional, engineered or grey infrastructure approaches.

These connections are supported by the UN Environment Programme (UNEP)'s Principles of Sustainable Insurance (PSI) initiative which highlights two roles for insurance in relation to nature (UNEP, 2024b):

1. **Enabler of economic activity:** Address nature-related issues, in particular nature-loss which would limit future economic activity; and
2. **Risk manager/carrier:** In particular for nature-related risks and losses by acting as a source of financial resilience for communities.

Marsh McLennan also developed the following framework that highlights pathways of how insurance solutions can support nature (Surminski et al., 2023).

Building resilience against nature loss

Novel insurance solutions help organizations protect their assets and operations from a growing range of nature impacts, while supporting their business efforts to reduce impacts on nature.

Restoring nature to build resilience against physical climate risks

Insurance solutions can incentivize nature restoration while reducing the impacts of climate extremes such as floods, droughts and wildfires, and helping organizations prepare for chronic climate trends like sea level rise.

Protecting nature to de-risk decarbonization efforts

A new class of risk transfer products aim to de-risk investments in nature-based solutions and carbon offsets.

Figure 4: Marsch McLennan Classification Criteria - Insurance and Nature (Surminski et al., 2023)

Initiatives like SCOR's Nature Restoration & Conservation Insurance Initiative exemplifies insurance as a de-risker and financing bridge. Their product insures ecosystem restoration projects by covering the costs needed to return ecosystems to their planned recovery trajectory after an insured event. This helps de-risk investments in restoration, making them more attractive to funders and stakeholders (SCOR, n.d.).

Looking in the other direction, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)'s BIOFIN initiative highlights how nature could reduce and manage risk for the insurance industry (UNDP BIOFIN et al., 2024):

1. **Managing physical risks:** Providing resilience against damages from catastrophes or extreme events and ensuring stability in high risk sectors, such as the agricultural sector.
2. **Managing transition risk:** Contributing towards an insurer's adaptation to changing regulatory and technological landscape through, for example, stable ecosystems providing predictable environmental conditions that enable accurate risk assessments and modelling.
3. **Managing systemic risk:** Preventing the long-run degradation of essential ecosystem services that support economic activity and financial resilience to disasters.

Several criteria for evaluating insurance schemes in their role of supporting nature can be identified (UNDP BIOFIN et al., 2024; UNEP, 2024b; ORRAA, n.d.-a):

1. **Alignment with biodiversity goals:**
 - Insurance schemes should support targets from the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.
 - They should contribute to ecosystem-based adaptation, mitigation, and disaster risk reduction.
2. **Nature-positive impact assessment:**
 - Products must demonstrate measurable positive impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. This includes evaluating impacts on nature.
3. **Risk transfer and restoration incentives:**
 - Insurance should not only compensate for damage but also incentivise upfront restoration and risk reduction. For example, parametric insurance models (e.g. coral reef insurance) are highlighted for their ability to trigger rapid restoration funding.
4. **Stakeholder engagement and governance:**
 - Effective schemes involve local communities, conservation experts, and policymakers.
 - Governance structures must ensure transparency and ecological integrity in restoration efforts.

In addition to the above criteria, the consideration of equity is necessary when designing insurance schemes that support nature. Ecosystem services are often distributed unequally across time, space and social groups (Thompson et al., 2023; Walker et al., 2024), and therefore the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework Target 22 pushes for an equitable decision-making process around investments in biodiversity (CBD, 2022).

5. Insights from design and implementation of different insurance schemes

5.1 Flood Re

Solution design & implementing risk-reduction

Flood Re, or the British Flood Reinsurance Pool, is a joint initiative between British insurers and the government, launched in 2016 to help secure the availability and affordability of flood insurance for individuals living in high-risk properties. In the arrangement, Flood Re acts as a reinsurer: in the event of a claim, Flood Re reimburses the insurer for the flood-related part. Flood Re was established to increase flood insurance penetration and serve as a temporary support mechanism during the transition to fully risk-reflective pricing, planned for 2039 or earlier, if its objectives are achieved before that date. While informed by public consultation, the design process was largely led by institutional stakeholders (insurers and the government), with limited participation from NGOs or communities.

The key objective of Flood Re is to support both market autonomy and insurance affordability, meaning that low- and normal-risk homes continue to be covered by standard insurance, while high-risk properties can be ceded to Flood Re for a fixed price based on the property's council tax band. These premiums, along with an annual levy of £135 million (approx. £8 - £10 per policy) collected from all home insurance providers, are the two main sources of funding for the scheme (Flood Re, 2018). Flood Re also invests its funds to generate additional income to cover claim payouts and improve its financial stability.

This funding mechanism ensures that the scheme is not directly funded by taxpayer money, reflecting the government's reluctance to assume financial responsibility for flood risk via claim payouts, instead focusing its role on delivering better flood defences (Surminski, 2018). Therefore, only the insured participate in the subsidy mechanism, with the government acting only as insurer of last resort in the event of significant flooding.

To fulfil its mandate, Flood Re focuses not just on price reduction, but also on reducing the physical risk of flooding (Flood Re, 2024b). To improve the resilience of at-risk households, the scheme runs the Build Back Better (BBB) initiative, aimed at increasing the number of homes with property-level flood resilience measures. In the event of a flood claim, BBB allows policyholders to install property-level flood resilience measures up to the value of £10,000, with current proposals to increase the sum to £15,000. It is estimated that 70% of policies ceded to the scheme are eligible for BBB, with some insurers deciding to extend the funding to all home flood claims, regardless of whether the policy has been ceded to Flood Re (Flood Re, 2024; Aviva, 2023). As part of BBB, Flood Re promotes various property flood resilience (PFR) measures: from the standard engineering like air bricks to NbS, such as flood resilient gardens (Flood Re, 2025).

Nature

While Flood Re was not originally designed to integrate NbS into its operation, recent developments within the scheme show growing support for recognizing the risk-reduction benefits of nature. Flood Re promotes the use of NbS as part of property-level flood resilience measures, such as rain gardens or retention ponds (Flood Re, 2024b). The scheme also showcased a flood-resilient garden at the 2024 Chelsea Flower Show to promote public understanding of NbS benefits and encourage wider discussion on their adoption as an individual-level resilience measure. In addition, recent company reports have placed greater emphasis on natural flood management (Flood Re, 2024c).

Performance

Since its launch, more than 500,000 households have benefited from the scheme, with four out of five homes with previous flood claims observing a price reduction of more than 50% (Flood Re, 2024). Before Flood Re, only 9% of households with a prior flood claim could obtain quotes from five or more insurers; since the launch of the scheme, 99% of high-risk households can get quotes from 15 or more insurance providers (UK Parliament, 2025). These statistics demonstrate that Flood Re has effectively increased affordability and availability of flood cover across the UK.

Yet, the scheme excludes properties built after 2009 to avoid incentivising new development in flood-prone areas. It is estimated that one in thirteen (8%) of new homes built since 2013 are located in a flood zone (Aviva, 2024), suggesting that the exclusion mechanism is not achieving its intended goal.

The initiative has not yet produced significant results. Implemented measures remain insufficient to keep pace with increasing damages, and only 10% of repeatedly flooded homes have adopted BBB (Flood Re, 2024). This echoes concerns that, in the long term, increasing insurance availability without proper investment in flood resilience measures might reduce the urgency to address the underlying causes of flooding, thereby creating moral hazard for both policyholders and policymakers alike (Jenkins et al., 2016). While BBB supports individual risk reduction, Flood Re does not currently incorporate comprehensive flood mitigation into its core model.

The scheme has been criticised for not sufficiently addressing the growing impact of climate change and the rising cost of flood risk. Some argue, this makes the transition to a risk-reflective market increasingly unachievable without stronger adaptation measures (OECD, 2020; Christophers, 2019). In fact, in its most recent reports, Flood Re's outlook on achieving an effective market is negative, given both market and resilience factors (Flood Re, 2025b).

Addressing equity

While Flood Re has succeeded in improving the affordability and accessibility of flood insurance in the UK, its design falls short of balancing actuarial equity with social justice fairness. Its funding system - where only the insured participate in the subsidy - ensures mutuality as defined by Linnerooth-Bayer et al. (2018). However, the scheme lacks a strong principle of accountability:

properties ceded to Flood Re are encouraged, but not required, to adopt risk-reduction measures. In addition, the exclusion of homes built after 2009 raises questions around solidarity and procedural equity of the scheme. While excluding such buildings, as well as commercial properties, Flood Re continues to provide coverage for high-value riverside mansions (Ralph, 2016). This falls short of achieving fairness as social justice, particularly under the premise of returning to a risk-reflective pricing framework.

Furthermore, Flood Re has minimal consideration of how to achieve co-benefits for nature in implementation. Without greater state investment in flood resilience - including large-scale nature-based solutions - and clearer strategies to manage climate risk, Flood Re may struggle to meet its objectives. Ultimately, its overall assessment and legacy will depend not just on market performance but also on delivering meaningful change to communities at risk.

5.2 CMCC - Community Insurance for Controlled Flooding

Solution design & implementing risk-reduction

Italy faces rising flood-risk from more intense and frequent extreme weather events due to climate change. Flood events across the Po river basin and Emiglio-Romagna as recent as 23/24 highlight the urgency of the threat. Traditional flood defences are proving inadequate, prompting a shift toward new adaptation measures such as controlled flooding and NbS that have the potential to reduce flooding risk while generating ecological and economic co-benefits.

Given high exposure to risk, insurance coverage in these areas remains limited and fragmented. To address this challenge, the NATURANCE Innovation Lab, initiated and led by CMCC, developed a community-based insurance scheme tied to controlled flooding operations and land renaturalization (Martin et al., 2025). To kick-off, CMCC held preliminary meetings with local/regional stakeholders, including expert contributions from related projects, such as LIFE CLIMAX Po, and international networks like NetworkNature. This was followed by a co-design process, targeting different stakeholder groups and fostering open dialogue to allow stakeholders to significantly contribute to the scheme's structure and adjust it iteratively. These dialogues brought together academics and adaptation experts, water boards, flood risk managers, and regional authority representatives, insurance companies and regulators.

In parallel, the Innovation Lab secured funding from NetworkNature Labs to support further development and testing at the international level. This next phase will include broader engagement with communities, particularly landowners and farmers, who are most directly affected by controlled flooding. Dedicated visuals will be created with graphic designers for more relatable communication. The process was designed to ensure a comprehensive and multifaceted perspective informing the co-production of a strategy that is both effective and equitable.

Public institutions played a central role in exploring the governance and operational feasibility of the scheme. Water boards were represented by National Association of the Agricultural Water

Board (ANBI) and regional branches in Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, and Lombardia, with participation from regional governments and the Po River Basin District Authority (AdBPo). The private sector contributed to the analysis of the actuarial and financial viability of the scheme. Assicurazioni Generali, which is developing a Climate Hub at the European level, contributed its perspective on innovation in insurance for climate adaptation. Financial regulators, including the Institute for Insurance Supervision (IVASS) and the Bank of Italy, were also involved. International networks added a broader perspective to the initiative. During discussions with NetworkNature Taskforce 3, it emerged that this work could link well with global financial policy initiatives such as the G20 Sustainable Finance Working Group.

The insurance approach follows a community-based, parametric scheme designed to support controlled flooding and the implementation of NbS. The proposal is based on an aggregator model in which water boards act as policyholders, purchasing insurance on behalf of the community. This model challenges regulatory barriers due to the limited remit of water boards in Italy, and necessitates a revisit on the evolving role of these institutions.

The parametric insurance product disburses payouts triggered by evidence-based threshold conditions, such as rainfall levels, which indicate when controlled flooding on upstream lands is required to prevent more severe damage downstream. This approach preserves the insurability principle of randomness¹, even though the flooding is a planned intervention, as the triggering of the payment is linked to exogenous climatological conditions enabling faster payouts and predictable financing for emergency operations.

The policy should cover the costs and liabilities associated with controlled flooding, including implementation, land and infrastructure restoration, and civil liability for unintentional damages to third parties. While it does not insure traditional private property losses, it contributes to downstream risk reduction by diverting excess water into pre-designated NbS zones. To meet future challenges related to climate change and nature loss, water boards could gradually shift from the role of water managers to a wider competence on the land and ecosystem services, tasked with building territorial resilience.

Nature

NbS are at the heart of the scheme's design, given their potential in enhancing water retention and buffering flood peaks, particularly when integrated into controlled flood zones. Flood-prone areas designated for controlled flooding would be converted from productive land to natural water retention infrastructure, generating ecosystem services such as biodiversity restoration, carbon storage, and recreation. These services could be monetised through biodiversity credits, payments for ecosystem services, or carbon markets, and used to compensate landowners, incentivise adoption of natural flood management measures, or offset insurance premiums. The current lack of standardised methods to quantify the overall risk reduction benefits of NbS

¹ Generally, insurers only insure 'pure risks' - the occurrence must be a fortuitous event, i.e. accidental or unexpected.

presents a challenge. Therefore there is a recognised need for robust, EU-wide methodologies and standards that could enable insurers to integrate NbS into pricing models in a transparent and reliable way.

The design of the scheme is also aligned with national/ EU policy developments, such as the EU Nature Restoration Law and EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) greening requirements, which prioritise ecological restoration and adaptive land management.

Performance

The scheme is currently in its design and testing phase, with the NATURANCE Innovation Lab laying a strong foundation for future implementation. The next steps include engaging a broader audience, particularly landowners affected by controlled flooding, and testing the proposal in communities highly exposed to flood risk. Further research will include a case study fieldwork aimed at exploring social preferences, assessing community acceptance, and further co-designing solutions that respond to real needs.

By shifting the focus from reactive damage compensation to proactive risk reduction, the scheme represents a significant advance in climate adaptation strategy. It offers financial protection to water boards and communities, while aligning with broader policy frameworks that support integrated, nature-based approaches to resilience, and presenting a model for equitable climate adaptation rooted in local governance and cross-sectoral collaboration.

Addressing equity

Equity and fairness were central to the design of the scheme, particularly in recognising the unequal distribution of costs and benefits between upstream (rural) and downstream (urban) communities.

Those expected to contribute financially are primarily landowners and businesses within the jurisdiction of water boards. They would pay an additional tribute, based on the benefits received from reduced flood risk, reflecting equity in outputs under the Stockholm Environmental Institute (2004) equity framework, and the proportional principle of distribution. The Classification Plan, already in use by water boards, provides the necessary data to calculate and justify this tribute in a transparent and equitable manner, reflecting the distributive and recognitional equity principles of the 'Schlosberg trio' (2003). For an effective and equitable application of the scheme, efforts should be made to keep contributions affordable, especially for residents in more vulnerable areas, in order to ensure the solidarity principle of the Linnerooth-Bayer et al (2018) framework is met.

Downstream urban communities are the primary beneficiaries, gaining protection from economic and material damage. Upstream landowners, while bearing the immediate burden of having their land flooded, also benefit from converting their fields into more flood-resilient landscapes and profiting from ecosystem services. Unlike land expropriation, this approach fosters dialogue and partnership, reflecting procedural equity and allowing landowners to co-develop a win-win

strategy that maintains profitability, while enhancing resilience. Compensation strategies for affected landowners are integral to this design, and could be supplemented by financial incentives such as payments for ecosystem services. The design of redistributive strategies relies on the Classification Plan to calculate each contributor's benefit from flood risk reduction. This prevents arbitrary or regressive charges and ensures proportionality in the tribute system.

5.3 ORRAA - Parametric Insurance for Coral Reef Recovery: The MAR Fund Model

Solution design & implementing risk-reduction

The Mesoamerican Reef Fund (MAR Fund) Insurance Programme represents a novel application of parametric insurance to ecosystem restoration, demonstrating how financial mechanisms can address critical gaps in post-disaster nature recovery. The MAR fund has been operational since 2021, providing funds for coral reef restoration in sites across Belize, Costa Rica, Colombia, Honduras, Guatemala and Mexico, supporting nearly 185,000 hectares of reefs which provide around US\$ 26 million in flood damage mitigation value annually. The solution design is based on a parametric insurance instrument for reefs. MAR Fund purchases sovereign risk-level insurance on behalf of the four countries in the MAR region from Willis Towers Watson (WTW), with premiums currently being paid for via the InsuResilience Solutions Fund (ISF) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (ISF, 2021; ORRAA, n.d.-b). The parametric model works on the basis of a cyclone reef damage design co-developed with WTW and local organisations who work in the vicinity of the reefs (Wharton, 2024).

The insurance mechanism employs a parametric structure that triggers payouts based on pre-defined hurricane parameters including wind speed, storm surge intensity, and proximity to protected reef sites, rather than requiring post-event damage assessments (ISF, 2021). This innovative approach addresses a critical gap in rapid disaster response by enabling immediate funding release for time-sensitive restoration activities such as coral fragment collection, nursery establishment, and structural reef repair (Wharton, 2024).

Nature

The programme explicitly recognises coral reefs as critical natural infrastructure, aligning with emerging policy frameworks that value ecosystem services in addition to traditional built/grey infrastructure. The parametric design represents one of the first applications of such insurance specifically for ecosystem restoration rather than traditional economic assets, reframing coral reefs as critical infrastructure worthy of dedicated risk financing protection (ORRAA, n.d.-b). This framing enables integration of ecological assets into risk financing mechanisms and national adaptation strategies, with coral reefs valued for their multiple services including coastal protection, fisheries support, and tourism revenue generation amounting to around US\$ 550 million over the next 50 years (ORRAA, n.d.-b; Wharton, 2024).

Scheme performance

Performance evaluation demonstrates clear operational success, with the programme completing its initial phase (2020-2025) and actively scaling to new geographies including Colombia through partnerships with Fondo Acción. Current expansion efforts across the broader Caribbean region indicate both technical success and stakeholder confidence in the approach. The programme exhibits adaptive management through geographic diversification and exploration of additional risk triggers, demonstrating institutional learning and model evolution (Wharton, 2024).

Addressing equity

The programme demonstrates strong attention to distributive concerns through its funding structure, where premium payments are entirely subsidised by international development finance, removing cost burdens from beneficiary countries and addressing fundamental affordability constraints in the Global South (ORRAA, n.d.-b). This demonstrates Linnerooth-Bayer et. al. (2018)'s solidarity principle and fairness as social justice within the risk-reflective pricing framework. Furthermore, local organisations that work closely with the reefs and the communities near them are able to access payouts from MAR funds through a rapid application process, easing fund disbursement (Wharton, 2024).

Yet, while the programme benefits over two million people indirectly through maintained ecosystem services, the mechanisms to ensure equitable distribution of benefits within these populations, particularly for marginalised groups, are not explicitly articulated. There is also currently no information surrounding whether local communities would be directly involved and if local and indigenous knowledge is being centred in the restoration processes in addition to typical technical expertise (Wharton, 2024). This makes it a challenge to accurately assess the programme's procedural equity.

5.4 InsuResilience - The Coffee Climate Protection Insurance (CCPI) Model

Solution design & implementing risk-reduction

The Coffee Climate Protection Insurance (CCPI) Programme represents a novel application of parametric insurance to smallholder agricultural protection, demonstrating how financial mechanisms can address critical gaps in climate risk management for vulnerable farming communities. The CCPI has been operational since 2021, providing protection for Robusta coffee farmers across Vietnam's Central Highlands, home to approximately 600,000 coffee-growing households who face increasing climate volatility that can reduce production by up to 25% during severe drought events (Barlis et al., 2022a).

The solution design is based on parametric insurance instruments for agricultural climate risks. The InsuResilience Solutions Fund purchases coverage on behalf of Vietnamese coffee farmers through WTW, with premiums currently being subsidised via international development finance including the German government and the Natural Disaster Fund managed by Global Parametrics. The

parametric model works on the basis of satellite-measured rainfall data co-developed with WTW, ECOM Agroindustrial Corp., and local organisations working with coffee farming communities, as well as the University of South Queensland (Barlis, 2021; WTW, 2025b).

The insurance mechanism employs a parametric structure that triggers payouts based on pre-defined rainfall parameters including cumulative precipitation rather than requiring post-event crop damage assessments. This innovative approach addresses a critical gap in agricultural loss response by enabling immediate funding release for time-sensitive recovery activities such as replanting, equipment replacement, and maintaining farm operations (Barlis et al., 2022b). The parametric design represents an application of such insurance specifically for smallholder agricultural protection rather than traditional commercial farming assets, reframing coffee production systems as climate-vulnerable livelihoods worthy of dedicated risk financing protection (WTW, 2025b). Premium payments are entirely subsidised by international development finance, removing cost burdens from smallholder farmers and addressing fundamental affordability constraints in developing countries (Lan et al., 2023).

Nature

There have been no mentions of nature-based solutions in publicly available documentation. Thus, while the insurance is for a plantation commodity, it does not seem to consider nature as part of its solution design at the moment (Barlis, 2021; Barlis et al., 2022a; Barlis et al., 2022b).

Performance

Performance evaluation demonstrates clear operational success, with the programme achieving its first payout in 2024 following drought conditions during the coffee flowering season and actively scaling from the initial 100-farmer pilot to coverage across five regions in the Central Highlands (WTW, 2025b). Current expansion efforts indicate both technical success and stakeholder confidence in the approach. The programme exhibits adaptive management through geographic diversification and exploration of co-contribution financing models, demonstrating institutional learning and model evolution towards sustainable premium financing involving farmers, traders, and roasters across the coffee value chain (Barlis et al., 2022a; Barlis et al., 2022b). The CCPI Programme offers a compelling demonstration that parametric insurance can be effectively adapted to smallholder agricultural contexts, provided sufficient technical capacity, institutional support, and financial backing exist. The model successfully addresses critical timing constraints in agricultural loss response while establishing smallholder farming systems as insurable climate-vulnerable assets.

Addressing equity

The innovative funding structure, where premium payments are entirely subsidised by international development finance, considers distributive equity making it financially accessible to coffee farmers and meets Linnerooth-Bayer et al (2018)'s solidarity principle. The programme explicitly recognises coffee production systems as critical agricultural infrastructure requiring

protection against increasing climate volatility, aligning with emerging policy frameworks that value agricultural resilience in addition to traditional sectors that receive insurance (Barlis et al., 2022a; Barlis et al., 2022b). Yet, while the programme benefits farmers directly through rapid payouts following climate events, the mechanisms to ensure equitable distribution of benefits within farming communities, particularly for marginalised groups and women farmers, are not explicitly articulated, meaning it is difficult to assess the procedural and recognitional equity of the scheme (Lan et al., 2023). There is also currently limited information surrounding whether local communities are directly involved in programme design and if local agricultural knowledge is being centred in risk management processes in addition to typical technical expertise. Future policy design would benefit from deeper integration of equity considerations, particularly around participation, representation, and benefit-sharing mechanisms to ensure such innovations are both effective and just.

5.5 Wesselényi Miklós Fund - Co-designing an Equitable National Flood Insurance System

Solution design & implementing risk-reduction

Hungary ranks only behind the Netherlands with respect to flood exposure in Europe. Over half of the country's territory, two-thirds of its arable land, and a third of its railways are exposed to riverine, ground water and flash floods. Early estimates showed that losses from flooding could reach almost a quarter of the GDP of river flood basins, or 7-9 percent of the total GDP of the country (Halcrow Water, 1999).

One of the highest flood risk areas in Hungary, and one of the poorest regions in Europe, is the Upper Tisza river basin in the northeastern part of the country, where there are more than 400 communities protected by nearly 3,000 km of flood defences (Global Water Partnership, 2025). Despite massive investments in flood protection levees and more recent investments in upstream reservoirs, floods continue to impose large losses on farmers and properties in the basin.

In Hungary, the central government takes primary responsibility for preventing floods through large investments in levees and, until recently, fully compensating victims for their losses. With escalating losses, this policy had become prohibitively expensive for the government budget, and continues to be viewed as encouraging undesired development in flood-risk areas.

Given the historical role of the central government in compensating flood losses and the limited role of private insurance, Hungary was considering introducing a nationwide flood insurance system. A three-year participatory process (2001-2004) was conducted to design an equitable system, consisting of face-to-face stakeholder interviews (24), a public survey (400 persons in high-risk and low-risk locations) and a stakeholder workshop (Linnerooth-Bayer et al. 2006; Ekenberg et al. 2003).

The stakeholder interviews revealed three distinctly different paths that the Hungarian policy community could take to reduce flood losses and provide support to flood victims in the Upper Tisza region: business-as-usual state protection, market-based individual responsibility, and shared responsibility with ecological development. Through the participatory process, four policy options were developed:

- Option A: Continues the practice of combining extensive government post-disaster relief with voluntary, flat-rate (cross-subsidized) insurance;
- Option B: Place more responsibility on households living in high-risk areas - the government compensates victims by a lesser amount, and the public role is supplemented by voluntary private insurance based on a flat-rate premium. If a household seeks greater coverage, risk-based insurance would be offered; and
- Option C: Reduce the role of private insurers with the creation of a fully public insurance system (government disaster fund) financed by mandatory, flat-rate contributions from all property owners throughout Hungary. The government subsidises insurance premiums for low-income households.
- Option D: The moderated workshop began with a discussion on a possible compromise, which led to an innovative new system - only households with private insurance would qualify for government assistance after a disaster, but the government would heavily subsidise poor households in their purchase of voluntary, private flood insurance. It was also agreed that the government would not provide reinsurance for private insurers. The consensus included government compensation only to insured households (50% of losses), a private insurance system with bundled or separate policies for all types of natural disaster risks (not modelled), covering approximately 50% of the damage, voluntary flat-rate premiums (0.01% of property value), no government reinsurance; and government subsidies for poor households up to 100% of premium.

Following the stakeholder workshop, and partly influenced by the results, the Hungarian government decided upon a flood insurance program for properties threatened by damage from riverine flood or standing water. According to legislation in 2003 (the Wesselényi Miklós Fund, Act LVIII), the government has fully underwritten flood insurance in high-risk areas where most private companies do not offer policies.

Nature

The region's early ecosystem of floodplains that supported forests, meadows, and fishponds could withstand occasional flooding, but land development has brought more settlements and intensive agricultural production that requires tightly regulated water levels and protection from seasonal floods. While the research reported here was conceived and carried out before recent attempts to shift the Tisza flood risk management to more environmentally oriented pathways, the stakeholder process identified "shared responsibility with ecological development" as one of three potential paths forward. Survey results revealed that increasing flood losses were primarily

attributed to ecological imbalance alongside insufficient development of flood defence levees and inappropriate land-use practices in the catchment area.

Performance

To date, uptake of the Wesselényi Miklós Fund insurance is low. In 2010, the number of properties insured by the scheme was 876, while the number of entitled property owners was over 100,000 (Vereczki, 2010). Its main limitation is that poor households only receive a 30% subsidy for their private, risk-based insurance premiums, in contrast to the stakeholder consensus of up to 100% subsidisation.

The great majority of Hungarians still feel that the government should be responsible for flood prevention and compensation, and in case of severe floods, the government still compensates flood victims. For example, during the 2010 summer floods and storms, when the estimated household losses totalled around €143 million, government subsidies reached around €11 million (Vereczki, 2010).

The public survey revealed strong support for government involvement: 57% believed the government should compensate all victims a certain percentage of their losses, while 19% supported combining compensation with insurance (Linnerooth-Bayer et al, 2006). Despite generous ex-post public support, early statistics showed that over 50% of households (though fewer in the Upper Tisza) carried residential property insurance often "bundled" with flood insurance that is required for homeowner mortgages.

Addressing Equity

The participatory process revealed complex and sometimes contradictory perspectives on equity. The majority of polled Hungarians (89%) would fully or partially support generous public compensation on grounds of social solidarity. Simultaneously, 90% of respondents fully or partially supported switching to more individual responsibility.

On the critical issue of premium pricing, opinions were divided: 47% believed equal premiums for high and low-risk areas would be unfair, while 25% supported cross-subsidisation based on social solidarity, and 13% supported it because high-risk area residents are poor. Notably, in high-risk regions, more people approved cross-subsidisation than in low-risk regions, with supporters constituting 67% of interviewees in the Upper Tisza region.

Views on equity appeared tightly coupled with views on responsibility. Since the government is viewed as liable if flood levees fail, it is responsible for compensating victims. As one of the participants remarked, "this policy will cost the government dearly in the short term, but it will create a culture of responsibility and insurance in the region over the medium term."

The heavy subsidisation of insurance premiums for poor households in the consensus proposal placated those with moral commitments to pro-poor policies and social justice. However, the implemented system's limitation to 30% premium subsidies for poor households, rather than the stakeholder-recommended 100%, represents a significant departure from the equity principles

established through the participatory process. While the system thus emphasised the procedural and recognitional forms of equity, in its final form, it fell short of ensuring solidarity and social justice considerations.

6. Discussion: emerging guidance for those tasked with exploring, designing and implementing insurance schemes

The case studies demonstrate that consideration of nature and equity during the design of innovative insurance schemes for climate adaptation is not only possible, but is already being implemented by forward thinking insurers, governments and local organisations. The design plays an important role in addressing the nature and biodiversity crisis and ensuring that costs and benefits are distributed equally when addressing climate adaptation risks. Whilst there are clear benefits of these innovative schemes, progress is often still in early stages with the need for further evidence of long term economic benefits. Nature is often considered sporadically instead of consistently and not all elements of equity are adequately balanced. There is a need for further standardisation of building nature and equity into the planning process and tracking performance over time (Rödl & Arlati, 2022; Kelso et al., 2024; Vicarelli et al., 2024).

Table 1 summarises the key design criteria of the case studies for the aspects of risk reduction, nature and equity, as well as general performance.

Table 1: Summary of case study insights

Case Study	Standard Aspects	Risk-reduction	Nature	Equity	Performance
Flood Re	Reinsurance for home insurance’s flood-risk component	Building Back Better	Promotes property level NbS, increased emphasis of large scale NbS in recent reports	Distributive equity, mutuality principle, actuarial fairness, fairness as social justice	The scheme remains financially solvent and has achieved considerable progress in terms of coverage.
Insurance for Controlled Flooding	Parametric product, payouts when controlled flooding is required	Severe damage downstream is prevented by controlled flooding upstream	Productive land is converted to natural water retention infrastructure	Proportional distributive equity, recognitional equity, solidarity principle, equity in outputs	Not yet assessed
ORRAA	Insurance for existing coral reef through parametric trigger	Preservation of risk-reducing capacity of reefs	Actively recognises the disaster risk mitigation value of coral reefs and supports its steady damage repairs after storms	Subsidised premiums reduce burdens on already vulnerable/financially stressed beneficiaries	Scheme has successfully disbursed funds after storms and remains financial solvent
Insu Resilience	Parametric drought insurance for coffee plantation small-holders	N/A	While the scheme considers plantations are needing protection, there is little mention of NbS	The premiums are subsidised heavily with development finance. Furthermore, parametric	The scheme has rapidly expanded across Central Vietnam beyond its 100-member pilot.

				triggers allow for rapid fund disbursement to farmers	
Wesselényi Miklós Fund	Mix of public and private insurance, with government subsidies for poor households	N/A	"Shared responsibility with ecological development" identified as one of three potential paths forward	The designed process emphasised procedural and recognitional equity. Subsidies aim to provide some form of solidarity	Low uptake due to low subsidies for poor households (only 30%)

Below we discuss five key learnings that have been identified from the case study assessment.

Multiple Configurations: Schemes exist in multiple configurations of private, public and third sector actors.

There exists significant variation in the configuration of climate adaptation insurance schemes, in terms of the division of responsibility for both financing and implementation. FloodRe for example takes the approach of an ‘arms-length’ public body funded by the insurance industry, but still subject to the same scrutiny of a public sector body (CII, 2025). Conversely, the CCPI is funded partly by premiums subsidised from development assistance, but jointly implemented by a development agency and WTW, a private insurance broking firm, reflecting a model that combines all three sectors (Barlis, 2021). Each of these models can offer different advantages and disadvantages. For example, the MAR fund and CCPI models allow for efficient collaboration between the private and third sector, evidenced by their pilots and quick calibration of parametric models, disbursement mechanisms and stakeholder consultations (Barlis, 2022b; Wharton, 2024). Flood Re, CMCC and Wesselényi Miklós Fund may have slower feedback loops, but are less likely to experience major funding crunches given that government backing allows for a greater trust and scope of the project (CII, 2025). It is crucial to consider which configuration offers the best fit for purpose for any insurance scheme given local context and needs.

Stakeholder Engagement: Stakeholder engagement varies significantly across schemes.

There is major variance in how and which stakeholders have been engaged in the design of solutions. Flood Re strongly reflects the priorities of insurance companies despite conducting a range of reviews involving both eligible and non-eligible households. The legal mechanisms that dictate its mandate remain fundamentally set by the insurance industry and the UK government with minimal influence from home-owners, renters and commercial entities (CII, 2025; Flood Re, 2018). On the other hand, CCPI and Wesselényi Miklós Fund represent a strong example of using stakeholder workshops to identify concerns and modify the scheme to better suit local needs, giving meaningful influence of the scheme’s design and operation to its beneficiaries (Barlis et al., 2022a; Barlis et al., 2022b). The engagement of stakeholders influences how an insurance scheme

evolves and whom it serves, which is a key question that needs consistent reflection over the course of a scheme's lifetime.

Integrating Nature: Nature is inconsistently considered, often being viewed secondary to climate.

The integration of nature into each scheme varies significantly and brings a variety of challenges to address. In some cases nature is seen as a core component, whilst in others it is excluded or seen as an afterthought. In CMCC, NbS forms a crucial part of the scheme, recognising their potential in enhancing water retention and buffering flood peaks. In the MAR Fund, the coral reef is recognised as a natural capital that requires maintenance just as much as any grey infrastructure, providing benefits being experienced by those who live on the coast or depend on the reef for their livelihood (ORRAA, n.d.-b). Contrarily, while Flood Re has begun to think about NbS at the property level, it is yet to have fully materialised in the scheme's implementation. There is a need to fully embed nature into the design of schemes, recognising co-benefits and trade-offs for both climate change and society in decision making (Flood Re, 2024; Flood Re, 2024c). Ongoing challenges include understanding where to implement NbS, the quantification of risk reduction and quantification of co-benefits and trade-offs between nature and other social issues. Projects require standardised metrics for cross-project/cross-temporal comparison and therefore conclusions based on current evidence may be premature (Rödl & Arlati, 2022; Kelso et al., 2024; Vicarelli et al., 2024).

Risk reduction: All case studies utilise risk-reduction to counteract the threats of climate change, but to different extents and in different ways.

This underscores the need for the insurance industry to adopt a consistent and proactive climate risk management strategy moving forward. Flood Re's adoption of the Build Back Better scheme reflects an emerging trend, using housing retrofitting as a strategy to improve resilience to flooding (Flood Re, 2024; Aviva, 2023). It has also begun to fold in NbS as part of its strategy, actively promoting retention ponds and flood-resilient gardens, indicating an active exploration of novel risk reduction strategies in synergy with nature (Flood Re, 2025). Unlike Flood Re which promotes targeted additional risk reduction, the MAR Fund targets the restoration of damaged coral reefs which provide a risk-reduction service at a regional scale. By preserving the integrity of corals through innovative funding mechanisms, the Fund is able to ensure they can continue to reduce risks against storms (ORRAA, n.d.-b; Wharton, 2024). The CMCC case highlights how risk-reduction could also happen in the form of anticipatory action and controlled risk acceptance. By compensating upper riparian land-holders to accept some flooding (i.e., a risk), the scheme transfers some of the disproportionate risk lower riparian land-holders face, and universally reduces risk by avoiding significant damages for either party (Martin et al., 2025). While risk-reduction is gaining prominence as a priority in insurance design, it needs to be fully integrated and its performance should be evidence in order to ensure the long term sustainability of projects.

Balancing Equity Principles: There is a need to balance the multiple aspects of equity – i.e. balancing between different principles of equity in insurance design and implementation.

Satisfying multiple dimensions of equity proves to be a balancing act, often pulling the scheme in different directions. Flood Re for example is mandated to move towards an actuarial fair pricing mechanism that is risk reflective, but must still be inclusive by promoting affordability and accessibility of home insurance (Flood Re, 2018). These two objectives can be at loggerheads. Not all aspects of equity can be easily met simultaneously, often necessitating iterative evolution of the scheme. For example, CCPI embodies recognitional justice by targeting coffee farmers, an under-insured sector increasingly facing climate risk and provides them with a parametric insurance model with premium-subsidies, reducing the financial and procedural burden on these farmers in accessing insurance or commensurate compensation. However, a focus on one area may not always be balanced with recognition of societal needs, such as recognition of gender or ethnic minorities (Barlis, 2021; Barlis et al., 2022a; Barlis et al., 2022b). This indicates that there is further work that needs to be done to recognise the unique needs of multiple groups concurrently and amending procedures and pipelines to ensure they are sufficiently included. Balancing equity priorities may not be straightforward and needs reflection on the scheme's objective and scope.

7. Challenges and opportunities for practically advancing equitable and sustainable insurance models

Whilst it is encouraging to see growing uptake and development of insurance models that address the multiple issues of climate risk and nature loss, this is a developing area still in its early stages. As insurers and policy makers are seeking to expand use of insurance for restoring nature as well as climate risk, there remain outstanding questions around effective design and implementation, including how to effectively embed equity principles. Designing insurance solutions that are both equitable and sustainable is a complex but an essential task.

Insights from the “Scaling Insurance Impact for Communities and Ecosystems” workshop, hosted by The Nature Conservancy and the Consensus Building Institute, underscore the multifaceted challenges and opportunities in embedding justice and fairness into insurance design.

- **Complexity of defining vulnerability:** One of the most pressing challenges is the nuanced nature of vulnerability, being at the intersection of multiple dimensions - race, gender identity, migration status, housing conditions, and more. These overlapping factors demand a context-specific approach to policy design. There is no universal formula for identifying who should be included in an insurance scheme; rather, each context requires careful, inclusive deliberation to ensure that no group is inadvertently excluded or underserved.
- **Reconciling diverse equity perspectives:** Equity can be interpreted differently depending on the role an actor holds. For example, a claims adjuster may focus on fairness in the payout process, while a modeller may prioritize long-term systemic impacts. These differing perspectives must be acknowledged and reconciled to ensure that equity is not only a shared goal but also a coordinated practice. Bridging these internal divides is critical to designing policies that are both just and effective.
- **Integration over addition:** A key tension for practitioners lies in whether equity should be integrated into the core of insurance decision-making or treated as an add-on. While the latter may offer a quicker path to implementation, it risks superficiality. Embedding equity into the DNA of insurance design, across underwriting, pricing, claims, and community engagement, offers a more transformative path. This approach fosters systemic change and ensures that equity is not sidelined when trade-offs arise.
- **Building Trust and Participation:** Equitable outcomes require more than affordability. They demand meaningful community participation, trust-building, and tailored engagement strategies. Insurance schemes must be co-designed with communities. This includes considering the appropriateness of triggers, claims processes, and coverage types. Without this participatory foundation, even well-intentioned policies may fail to address the needs of those most at risk.
- **Addressing data gaps and biases:** Data remains a critical bottleneck. Existing datasets often fail to capture the full spectrum of vulnerability, leading to skewed risk assessments and potentially unjust outcomes. Without better data, insurance solutions risk reinforcing

the very inequalities they aim to mitigate. Investments in inclusive data collection and participatory risk modelling are essential steps forward.

- **Ensuring financial safeguards:** Equitable insurance solutions often require financial support mechanisms such as public subsidies, grants, or philanthropic funding. These resources must be allocated with care, guided by safeguards that ensure they reach the most vulnerable. The development and philanthropic sectors have a vital role to play in ensuring that funding mechanisms do not inadvertently exacerbate inequities but instead serve as tools for empowerment and resilience.

There is no single blueprint for embedding equity and sustainability into nature-based insurance solutions. Instead, what is needed is a willingness to revisit foundational assumptions, challenge existing logics, and foster continuous dialogue among practitioners, communities, policymakers, and donors. As climate and nature-related risks escalate, the urgency to develop insurance models that are not only technically sound but also socially legitimate becomes critical.

Looking forward, schemes should ensure they balance principled ambition with pragmatic design to ensure that insurance solutions are not only financially viable, but also ecologically grounded and just, inclusive, and resilient over the long term.

References

- Aviva. (2023). *Our Build Back Better commitment*. Aviva. Retrieved August 25, 2025, from <https://connect.avivab2b.co.uk/broker/articles/news/our-build-back-better-commitment/>
- Aviva (2024). *One in thirteen new homes built in flood zone* [Press release]. <https://www.aviva.com/newsroom/news-releases/2024/01/one-in-thirteen-new-homes-built-in-flood-zone/>
- Barlis, A. (2021). Coffee Climate Protection Insurance (CCPI) scheme led by the private sector in the Central Highlands, Vietnam covered 200 hectares of farms of coffee producers protecting them from the risk of drought and excessive rainfall. In *CGSpace*. CGSpace. <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/5e032880-9708-4ca9-8766-6409ab550169/content>
- Barlis, A., Swaans, C., Kath, J., Mushtaq, S., & Deniau, A. (2022a). *Applying seasonal climate forecasting and innovative insurance solutions to climate risk management in the agriculture sector in Southeast Asia* [Agriculture]. InsuResilience. https://www.insuresilience.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/CaseStudy_Vietnam_FINAL.pdf
- Barlis, A., Mushtaq, S., Bossolasco, L., Kath, J., Roberts, J., Wilkinson, C., & Swaans, C. (2022b). DeRisking Coffee in the Central Highlands: Piloting a Coffee Climate Protection Insurance (CCPI) for farmers and agribusinesses. In *climatechange.vn*. IKI - Vietnam. <https://www.climatechange.vn/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/DeRisking-coffee-in-the-Central-Highlands-Piloting-a-coffee-climate-protection-insurance-for-farmers-and-agribusinesses.pdf>
- Beck, M. W., Narayan, S., Trespalacios, D., Pfliegner, K., Losada, Í. J., Menéndez, P., Espejo, A., Torres, S., Díaz-Simal, P., Fernández, F., Abad, S., Mucke, P., & Kirch, L. (2018). *The global value of mangroves for risk reduction: Summary report* [PDF]. The Nature Conservancy. <https://doi.org/10.7291/V9930RBC>
- Betram, V., & Scott, Z. (2024). Rethinking premium support: enhancing the impact and sustainability of climate risk insurance. In Centre for Disaster Protection. Centre for Disaster Protection. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/61542ee0a87a394f7bc17b3a/t/66ec25d4ebb6b7425928f82f/1726752217857/RETHINKING+PREMIUM+SUPPORT.pdf>
- Bouchard, F., Surminski, S., Fleming, R., Raisinghani, G., & Dabral, A. (2022). Supporting materials, capabilities framework and pioneer projects Fulfilling a legacy of societal risk management: Mobilizing insurance sector capabilities to advance Community-Level climate risk reduction and adaptation. In *UN Climate Change High-Level Champions*. Marsh McLennan. <https://www.marshmclennan.com/web->

[assets/insights/publications/2022/november/Race%20to%20Resilience%20Report_COP27%20FINA_L.pdf](#)

Brundtland, G. H. (1987). *Our common future: Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development* (UN Document A/42/427). United Nations. <https://www.un-documents.net/our-common-future.pdf>

Charpentier, A., Barry, L., & James, M. R. (2021). Insurance against natural catastrophes: balancing actuarial fairness and social solidarity. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance Issues and Practice*, 47(1), 50–78. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41288-021-00233-7>

Chartered Insurance Institute (CII). (2025). *Insurance underwriting process* (2025 ed.). CII Learning Solutions. <https://www.cii.co.uk/learning/qualifications/unit-insurance-underwriting-process-if3/>

ClimateWise. (2012). "Compendium of Disaster Risk Transfer Initiatives in the Developing World." Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership. <https://www.cisl.cam.ac.uk/business-action/sustainable-finance/climatewise/pdfs/climatewise-compendium-of-disaster-risk-transfer.xlsm/view>

Cobbing, P., O'Hare, P., Parkington, S., Comyn, F., & Maynard, P. (2024). *Rochdale Flood poverty Report*. https://nationalfloodforum.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/Rochdale_Flood_Poverty_Report.pdf

Coggins, S., Berrang-Ford, L., Hyams, K., Satyal, P., Ford, J., Paavola, J., Arotoma-Rojas, I., & Harper, S. (2021). Empirical assessment of equity and justice in climate adaptation literature: a systematic map. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(7), 073003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac0663>

Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). (2022). *Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* (Decision CBD/COP/15/L.25). Adopted at the 15th meeting of the Conference of the Parties (COP 15), Montreal. Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/conferences/2021-2022/cop-15/documents>

de Herve, M. (2021). Fair strategies to tackle unfair risks? Justice considerations within flood risk management. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 69, 102745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102745>

Ekenberg, L., Brouwers, L., Danielson, M., Hansson, K., Johansson, J., Riabacke, A., & Vári, A. (2003). Flood risk management policy in the Upper Tisza Basin: A system analytical approach. Simulation and analysis of three flood management strategies. <https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/7078/>

- European Environment Agency. (2024). European Climate Risk Assessment. In *European Environmental Agency*. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment?activeTab=13e424cd-5934-4614-92ef-e6be8d05c441>
- FEMA. (1968). National Flood Insurance Act of 1968. <https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-07/national-flood-insurance-act-1968.pdf>
- Flood Re. (2018). *How is Flood Re funded?* Flood Re. Retrieved July 12, 2025, from <https://www.floodre.co.uk/faq/how-is-flood-re-funded/>
- Flood Re. (2024). *Transition*. In *Annual Review and Accounts 2024*. Retrieved July 2025, from <https://www.floodre.co.uk/ara-2024/transition/>
- Flood Re. (2024b). *The Quinquennial Review* [PDF]. https://www.floodre.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/Flood-Re_QQR-2024_Digital.pdf
- Flood Re. (2024c). *ClimateWise Principles 2024 response report: June 2023-June 2024* [PDF]. Flood Re. Retrieved August 25, 2025, from <https://www.floodre.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/Flood-Re-ClimateWise-report.pdf>
- Flood Re. (2025a). *Be Flood Smart: Property flood resilience | Home flood defences*. Retrieved July 25, 2025, from <https://www.floodre.co.uk/be-flood-smart/>
- Flood Re. (2025b). *Flood Re Limited Annual Report and Financial Statements*. <https://www.floodre.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/Flood-Re-Limited-ARA-2025-FINAL-EY-signed.pdf>
- Forster, P. M., Smith, C., Walsh, T., Lamb, W. F., Lamboll, R., Cassou, C., Hauser, M., Hausfather, Z., Lee, J., Palmer, M. D., Von Schuckmann, K., Slangen, A. B. A., Szopa, S., Trewin, B., Yun, J., Gillett, N. P., Jenkins, S., Matthews, H. D., Raghavan, K., . . . Zhai, P. (2025). Indicators of Global Climate Change 2024: annual update of key indicators of the state of the climate system and human influence. *Earth System Science Data*, 17(6), 2641–2680. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2641-2025>
- Gallagher Re. (2025). *Natural Catastrophe and Climate Report: 2024: Data, Insights and Perspectives*. <https://www.aig.com/gallagherre/-/media/files/gallagher/gallagherre/news-and-insights/2025/natural-catastrophe-and-climate-report-2025.pdf>
- Global Water Partnership. (2025). Controlling floods and pollution in Europe’s Tisza Basin. Retrieved August 25, 2025, from <https://www.gwp.org/en/we-act/our-results/our-impact/explore-gwp-impact-stories/controlling-floods-and-pollution-in-europes-tisza-basin2/>

Government Accountability Office. (2020). FEMA's New Rate Setting Methodology Improves Actuarial Soundness but Highlights Need for Broader Program Reform. In GAO (GAO-23-105977). <https://www.gao.gov/assets/gao-23-105977.pdf>

Grasso, M. (2010). An ethical approach to climate adaptation finance. *Global Environmental Change*, 20(1), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2009.10.006>

Howarth, C., Robinson, E.J.Z. (2024) Effective climate action must integrate climate adaptation and mitigation. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 14, 300–301. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-01963-x>

IFRC. (2025). *In a climate of shrinking funds and increasing risk, it's time to shift priorities and get ahead of disasters.* <https://www.ifrc.org/article/ifrc-climate-shrinking-funds-and-increasing-risk-its-time-shift-priorities-and-get-ahead>

InsuResilience Global Partnership. (2023). *Glossary: Common terms and acronyms of climate and disaster risk finance and insurance.* <https://www.insuresilience.org/knowledge/glossary/>

InsuResilience Solution Fund. (2021, May 31). Project Brief C3.25 MAR Fund – InsuResilience. <https://insuresilience-solutions-fund.org/2021/05/31/project-brief-c3-25-mar-fund/>

IPBES (2019): Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. S. Díaz, J. Settele, E. S. Brondízio, H. T. Ngo, M. Guèze, J. Agard, A. Arneth, P. Balvanera, K. A. Brauman, S. H. M. Butchart, K. M. A. Chan, L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii, J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, G. F. Midgley, P. Miloslavich, Z. Molnár, D. Obura, A. Pfaff, S. Polasky, A. Purvis, J. Razzaque, B. Reyers, R. Roy Chowdhury, Y. J. Shin, I. J. Visseren-Hamakers, K. J. Willis, and C. N. Zayas (eds.). *IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 56 pages.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553579>

IPCC. (2022). Summary for policymakers. In H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E. S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, & B. Rama (Eds.). *Climate change 2022: Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (pp. 3–33). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.001>

Irianto, Okto & Adiatma, Tini. (2023). Financial Sustainability Publication Trend: A Bibliometric Study. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*. 12. 132. 10.36941/ajis-2023-0132.

IUCN (2020). *Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions. A user-friendly framework for the verification, design and scaling up of NbS. First edition.* Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.

Jarzabkowski, P., Chalkias, K., Clarke, D., Centre for Disaster Protection, Insurance Development Forum, InsuResilience Global Partnership, & InsuResilience Global Partnership. (2019). *Insurance*

for Climate adaptation: Opportunities and Limitations. <https://www.insdevforum.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Insurance-for-Climate-Adaptation-Opportunities-and-Limitations.pdf>

Jenkins, K., Surminski, S., Hall, J., & Crick, F. (2016). *Assessing the insurance role of the UK's Flood Re scheme* (Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment Working Paper No. 223). London School of Economics and Political Science.

<https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Working-Paper-223-Jenkins-et-al.pdf>

Juhola, S., Heikkinen, M., Pietilä, T., Groundstroem, F., & Käyhkö, J. (2022). Connecting climate justice and adaptation planning: An adaptation justice index. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 136, 609–619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.07.024>

Kelso, M. A., Stovall, A. E., Reguero, B. G., Franco, G., & Beck, M. W. (2024, February 7). *Nature-Based Solutions & Risk Management: Recommendations for Integrating Nature into Risk Science & Insurance*. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9305j0t4>

Lan, L., Mushtaq, S., Wang, Q., Barlis, A., Deniau, A., Byrareddy, V. M., Anh, H. T., & Swaans, K. (2023). Are Vietnamese coffee farmers willing to pay for weather index insurance? *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 100, 104185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2023.104185>

Linnerooth-Bayer, J., Surminski, S., Bouwer, L. M., Noy, I., & Mechler, R. (2018). Insurance as a response to loss and damage? In *Climate risk management, policy and governance* (pp. 483–512). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72026-5_21

Linnerooth-Bayer, J., Vári, A. and M. Thompson (2006). Floods and Fairness in Hungary. in *Clumsy Solutions for a Complex World: Governance, Politics and Plural Perceptions*, M. Verweij and M. Thompson, Eds. Palgrave Macmillan.

Marchal, R., Moncoulon, D., Gunn, E. L., Weinberg, J., Thakar, K., Altamirano, M., & Piton, G. (2023). Insurance and the natural assurance value (of ecosystems) in risk prevention and reduction. In *Water security in a new world* (pp. 35–50). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25308-9_3

Marchal, R., Piton, G. G., Lopez-Gunn, E., Zorrilla-Miras, P., Van Der Keur, P., Dartee, K., Pengal, P., Matthews, J., Tacnet, J., Graveline, N., Altamirano, M., Joyce, J., Nanu, F., Groza, I., Pena, K., Cokan, B., Burke, S., & Moncoulon, D. (2019). The (Re)Insurance Industry's Roles in the Integration of Nature-Based Solutions for Prevention in Disaster Risk Reduction—Insights from a European Survey. *Sustainability*, 11(22), 6212. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11226212>

Martin, C., Small, A., Deltenre, L., Thompson, N., Seega, N., Bastanzi, G., Biddau, F., Ceolotto, S., Wood, J., Mysiak, J., Staccione, A., Gunn, N., Calam, S., Pollard, J., Martin, H., Surminski, S., &

Kozłowska, Z. (2025). Scorecard publication on each business case, labs round II. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15740341>

Munang, R., Thiaw, I., Alverson, K., Liu, J., & Zhen. (2013) The role of ecosystem services in climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 5,(1). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877343513000080>

Narayan, S., Beck, M. W., Wilson, P., Thomas, C. J., Guerrero, A., Shepard, C. C., Reguero, B. G., Franco, G., Ingram, J. C., Trespalacios, D., & Burks-Copes, K. A. (2017). The value of coastal wetlands for flood damage reduction in the Northeastern USA. *Scientific Reports*, 7, 9463.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-09269-z>

O'Hare, P., & White, I. (2017). Beyond 'just' flood risk management: the potential for—and limits to—alleviating flood disadvantage. *Regional Environmental Change*, 18(2), 385–396.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-017-1216-3>

O'Neill, J., & O'Neill, M. (2012). Social justice and the future of flood insurance. In *www.jrf.org.uk* [Journal-article]. <https://philpapers.org/archive/ONESJA.pdf>

OECD. (2020). *Transition effects of Flood Re in the United Kingdom* [Report]. OECD Publishing.

https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2020/05/ocean-policies_18ba8794/transition-effects-of-flood-re-in-the-united-kingdom_24f3a4e1/fc416422-en.pdf

Ooms, V., Endendijk, T., Aerts, J., Botzen, W., & Robinson, P. (2025). Assessing effects of nature-based and other municipal adaptation measures on insured heavy rain damages. *EGUsphere*.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-1882>

ORRAA. (n.d.-a). *Homepage - ORRAA*. <https://oceanriskalliance.org/>

ORRAA. (n.d.-b). *Scaling coral reef insurance in the Caribbean - ORRAA*.

<https://oceanriskalliance.org/project/scaling-coral-reef-insurance-in-the-caribbean/>

Ralph, O. (2016, April 4). Flood Re expects 350,000 properties to be put into the scheme. *Financial Times*. <https://www.ft.com/content/3c72961a-f820-11e5-96db-fc683b5e52db>

Rödl, A., & Arlati, A. (2022). A general procedure to identify indicators for evaluation and monitoring of nature-based solution projects. *AMBIO*, 51(11), 2278–2293.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-022-01740-0>

Schäfer, L., Waters, E., Kreft, S., & Zissener, M. (2016). Making climate risk insurance work for the most vulnerable: Seven guiding principles (Munich Climate Insurance Initiative/UNU_EHS

Publication Series. Policy Report 2016, No. 1 United Nations University, 2016). Retrieved from <https://collections.unu.edu/view/UNU:5830>

Schlosberg, D. (2003). The justice of environmental justice: reconciling equity, recognition, and participation in a political movement. *Moral and political reasoning in environmental practice*, 77(106), 125-156.

SCOR. (n.d.). *Nature Restoration & Conservation Insurance Initiative | SCOR*. <https://www.scor.com/en/nature-restoration-conservation-insurance-initiative>

Scott, Z., Panwar, V., Weingärtner, L., & Wilkinson, E. (2022). *The political economy of premium subsidies: searching for better impact and design* (By ODI & InsuResilience Global Partnership). ODI. https://www.insuresilience.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/PEA_PremiumSubsidies_TP2-2022-12-22-14_06_52.pdf

Shawoo, Z., Browne, K., Canales, N., & Nazareth, A. (2024). A framework for distributive equity of adaptation finance. In *SEI* [Report]. Stockholm Environmental Institute. <https://www.sei.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/framework-distributive-equity-adaptation-finance-sei2024-050.pdf>

Surminski, S. & Hudson, P. (2017). Investigating the risk reduction potential of disaster insurance across Europe. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance - Issues and Practice* . pp. 1-28. ISSN 1018-5895 DOI: 10.1057/s41288-016-0039-7

Surminski, S. & Oramas-Dorta, D. (2011). "Building effective and sustainable risk transfer initiatives in low- and middle-income economies: what can we learn from existing insurance schemes?," [LSE Research Online Documents on Economics](https://www.lse.ac.uk/ResearchOnline/Documents/46401) 46401, London School of Economics and Political Science, LSE Library.

Surminski, S. (2013). The role of insurance in reducing direct risk: the case of flood insurance [Journal-article]. *International Review of Environmental and Resource Economics*, 7–7(3–4), 241–278. https://eprints.lse.ac.uk/60764/1/Surminski_Role-of-insurance-reducing-direct-risk_2014.pdf

Surminski, S. (2018). Fit for purpose and fit for the future? An evaluation of the UK's new Flood Reinsurance pool. *Risk Management and Insurance Review*, 21(1), 33–72. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rmir.12093>

Surminski, S., Panda, A., & Lambert, P. J. (2019). *Disaster insurance in developing Asia: An analysis of market-based schemes* (ADB Economics Working Paper Series No. 590). Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/528026/ewp-590-disaster-insurance-developing-asia.pdf>

Surminski, S., Saffioti, C., & Juay, R. (2023). Rooted in Resilience: Innovations in nature insurance for business. In *Marsh McLennan*. <https://www.marshmclennan.com/web->

[assets/insights/publications/2023/may/2023-rooted-in-resilience-innovations-in-nature-insurance-for-business.pdf](#)

Svarstad, H., & Benjaminsen, T. A. (2019). Reading radical environmental justice through a political ecology lens. *Geoforum*, 108, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2019.11.007>

Taskforce on nature-related financial disclosure (TNFD). (2023) *Recommendations of the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures*. [Disclosure recommendations – TNFD](#)

The Nature Conservancy. (2020, October 22). Could insuring mangroves protect coastal communities? *The Nature Conservancy*. <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-insights/perspectives/three-things-insuring-mangrove-forests/>

Thompson, A., Bunds, K., Larson, L., Cutts, B., & Hipp, J. A. (2023). Paying for nature-based solutions: A review of funding and financing mechanisms for ecosystem services and their impacts on social equity. *Sustainable Development*, 31(4), 1991–2066. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2510>

Tyllianakis, E., Martin-Ortega, J., & Banwart, S. A. (2022). An approach to assess the world's potential for disaster risk reduction through nature-based solutions. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 136, 599–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.07.021>

UK Parliament. (2025). *Draft Flood Reinsurance (Amendment) Regulations 2025* [House of Commons, Fourth Delegated Legislation Committee]. *Hansard*. Retrieved from [https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2025-02-26/debates/8088d86a-4129-41b3-972b-26d023a89936/DraftFloodReinsurance\(Amendment\)Regulations2025](https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2025-02-26/debates/8088d86a-4129-41b3-972b-26d023a89936/DraftFloodReinsurance(Amendment)Regulations2025)

UNDP BIOFIN, UNDP IRFF, & AB Entheos. (2024). How Insurance Can Address Nature-Related Risks: A Summary guide. In *United Nations Development Programme* [Report]. United Nations Development Programme. https://irff.undp.org/sites/default/files/2025/May/HOW-INSURANCE-CAN-ADDRESS-NATURE-RELATED-RISKS_0.pdf

UNDP. (2022). *Insurance and risk finance facility: Unlocking insurance and risk finance solutions for sustainable development*. United Nations Development Programme.

UNEP. (2020) *Six ways nature can protect us from climate change*. <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/six-ways-nature-can-protect-us-climate-change>

UNEP. (2024a). *Adaptation Gap Report 2024*. UNEP - UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/resources/adaptation-gap-report-2024>

UNEP. (2024b). *Insuring a resilient Nature-Positive future*. Geneva. https://betterinsurancenetwork.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Insurance-for-Nature-Positive_Priority-Actions-for-Insurance.pdf

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR). (2017). The Sendai Framework Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction. "Risk transfer". Accessed 26 September 2025. <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/risk-transfer>.

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR). (2024). *Disaster Risk*. PreventionWeb. <https://www.preventionweb.net/understanding-disaster-risk/component-risk/disaster-risk>

University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (CISL). (2022). *Integrating Nature: The case for action on nature-related financial risks*. Cambridge: University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership

UNU-EHS. (2025). 4 Critical dimensions for designing and implementing premium support for climate risk insurance. United Nations University. <https://unu.edu/ehs/article/4-critical-dimensions-designing-and-implementing-premium-support-climate-risk-insurance>

Vereczki, A. (2010): Biztosítás és a szélsőséges időjárás (Insurance and Extreme Weather). *Klíma-21 Füzetek* ('Climate 21 Booklets') (63), pp. 73–82.

Vicarelli, M., Sudmeier-Rieux, K., Alsadadi, A., Shrestha, A., Schütze, S., Kang, M. M., Leue, M., Wasielewski, D., & Mysiak, J. (2024). On the cost-effectiveness of Nature-based Solutions for reducing disaster risk. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 947, 174524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174524>

Walker, S., Smith, E., Bennett, N., Bannister, E., Narayana, A., Nuckols, T., Velez, K. P., Wrigley, J., & Bailey, K. (2024). Defining and conceptualizing equity and justice in climate adaptation. *Global Environmental Change*, 87, 102885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2024.102885>

WEF (2020) The Future of Nature and Business. Retrieved from: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_The_Future_Of_Nature_And_Business_2020.pdf

Wharton, J. (2024). The MAR Insurance Programme: a nature-based solution to enhance resilience. In M. J. González & C. Ruiz (Eds.), *MAR Insurance Programme* (pp. 2–5). MAR Fund. <https://marfund.org/en/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/MARInsurance-Brief-2024-a.pdf>

Willis Tower Watson. (2025b). *Willis and Global Parametrics deliver new parametric solution to coffee farmers in Vietnam*. WTW. <https://www.wtwco.com/en-za/news/2025/02/willis-and-global-parametrics-deliver-new-parametric-solution-to-coffee-farmers-in-vietnam>

WTW. (2025a). *With 2024 the first year to exceed 1.5°C warming, the insurance protection gap for natural catastrophes stands at 60%, according to WTW Natural Catastrophe Review*. <https://www.wtwco.com/en-id/news/2025/01/with-2024-the-first-year-to-exceed-1-point-5-degree-celcius-warming-the-insurance-protection-gap>

WWF (2020) Too hot to handle: A deep dive into biodiversity in a warming world. Living planet report. [Nature loss & climate change: linked problems, linked solutions | WWF \(panda.org\)](#)